

REFORMING THE EU RETURN REGULATION: ENSURING RIGHTS-BASED ALTERNATIVES TO DETENTION

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Key issues:

- In March 2025, the European Commission published a proposal for a Return Regulation to repeal the current Return Directive.
- The proposal allows alternative measures to pre-removal detention to be applied even without detention grounds, turning them into tools that extend restrictions on personal liberty rather than genuine substitutes for detention.
- Rights-based alternatives are largely absent in the proposal, including in the context of child detention where no child-specific measures are foreseen.
- Several proposed measures amount to alternative forms of detention rather than true alternatives to detention, given their intrusiveness and coercive nature.
- The ongoing negotiations present a key opportunity to enshrine genuine rights-based alternatives, limiting their impact on the right to liberty and fully guaranteeing procedural safeguards.

In March 2025, the European Commission published a proposal for a Return Regulation to repeal the current Return Directive. The stated goal is to streamline return processes and to enhance the return rate (currently 24%). One of its key components is to ensure the availability of third-country nationals subject to a return procedure by "laying down details for an efficient use of alternatives to detention". Alternative measures, although missing an official definition, are commonly understood as non-custodial measures entailing a lower degree of coerciveness than detention. As the current Return Directive lacks a legal framework for alternative measures, its inclusion under the proposed Regulation is certainly a welcome development.

This Policy Brief, nevertheless, criticises the proposed rules, arguing that they lean towards a securitarian approach. Indeed, alternatives are not portrayed as safeguards of the right to liberty but as mechanisms of control. As they are currently framed, they risk being applied disproportionately, procedurally inconsistently and with insufficient safeguards. A revision is necessary and presents an opportunity to incorporate rights-based measures, which have been shown to enhance compliance with the return procedure. If the EU fails, the "alternatives" will become a means to extend coercive measures beyond existing detention limits, thereby normalising indefinite restrictions on the right to liberty.

THE CURRENT NEAR-NON-APPLICATION RATE OF ALTERNATIVE MEASURES

Based on the scarce data collected by the European Migration Network and Frontex, the application rate for alternative measures was below 7% in 2019. Yet, the EU Court of Justice (EJJC) has clarified that alternative measures should be preferred to detention whenever possible. Member States often justify their scarce application by invoking the risk of absconding. However, since the majority of them do not record the number of individuals who actually abscond, this justification is weak. The limited data available indicate that the number of absconding cases is, in fact, low. Nevertheless, the proposal emphasises the need to address this issue.

Since the current Return Directive does not provide a legal framework for alternative measures, the introduction of such a framework is welcome – especially considering that when less coercive measures are available but not ordered, detention must be deemed unlawful and ceased immediately. A robust framework for alternative measures should, therefore, contribute to a reduced reliance on detention.

FRAMING ALTERNATIVE MEASURES WITHOUT THEIR LEGAL CONSTITUTIVE ELEMENT

The Commission's proposal lists five alternative measures: reporting obligations, surrender of documents, residence at a designated place, financial guarantees and electronic monitoring.

At first glance, this seems to be a breakthrough compared to the vague wording of the current directive, referring only to "other sufficient but less coercive measures". Yet, the way these alternatives are framed reveals legal flaws that undermine their very purpose. The most worrisome is the omission to link their application to the requirement that the grounds for detention are met.

Without mentioning this constitutive element, these 'alternatives' risk becoming measures that are applied arbitrarily and disproportionately. This risk is not hypothetical. The proposal explicitly allows their application even after the maximum detention period has been reached, without imposing any time-limits. As a result, these measures are no longer replacing detention but may instead operate as additional coercive measures, indefinitely extending restrictions on the right to liberty.

Furthermore, the proposed framework provides weaker legal safeguards than those governing detention. While alternatives require only an initial review within two months, detention is subject to periodic reviews every three months following the first review. The same procedural safeguards should apply in both cases.

FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS RISKS EMBEDDED IN THE PROPOSED MEASURES

There are several problematic policy choices underlying the legal framework, as the strict implementation of the proposed measures may violate fundamental rights. First, the requirement to "reside in a place designated by the authorities" may result in house arrest.

Even if the degree of this restriction on liberty may be proportional in a specific case, it still constitutes a deprivation of liberty outside any formal detention procedure. Second, financial guarantees risk excluding individuals who cannot afford them, thereby generating discrimination. Lastly, electronic monitoring carries the risk of stigmatisation through associations with criminality, while indiscriminate data collection may infringe on data protection rights. Due to its harshness and intrusiveness, electronic monitoring is moreover classified as an alternative form of detention.

The shortcomings of the proposal are especially striking in relation to children. Although it charts special rules for their return, it does not prohibit child detention. Instead, the proposal merely states that detention must be used as a measure of last resort and for the shortest possible time. Yet, these requirements are not specific to the detention of children: they apply to all return cases, as the proportionality principle governs the entire return procedure. The situation is further exacerbated by the absence of any children-specific alternative measures. This policy choice is difficult to reconcile with the best interests of the child, as enshrined in the Convention on the Rights of the Child, which the proposal claims to uphold.

Furthermore, the proposed alternative measures largely overlap with obligations listed in the proposal that require individuals to remain available during the return procedure, such as restrictions to a specific geographical area, residence at a designated address, and reporting to the competent authority at reasonable intervals. These obligations apply automatically to anyone subject to return until the end of the procedure, yet they may impose restrictions similar in nature to the designated “alternatives”. When alternative measures can be imposed even in the absence of detention grounds, the distinction between these various control measures becomes blurred. This overlap shows that all measures under consideration are primarily designed to prevent absconding, while sidestepping the necessary safeguards. However, the case law of the EUCJ and the European Court of Human Rights is unequivocal in requiring that measures restricting the right to liberty must be assessed on an individual basis, proportionate and time-limited.

Thus, the proposal reframes the risk of absconding from a specific ground for detention into a blanket objective justifying widespread control. Within this new narrative, imposing alternative measures outside the detention framework appears justified. However, this alarming shift marks a move away from a framework centred on safeguarding the right to liberty towards a framework centred on control, one that enables indefinite and largely automated restrictions on the right to liberty.

A welcome step in the proposal is the introduction of an obligation upon the Member States to report to Eurostat, on a quarterly basis, the number of irregular migrants subjected to detention and to alternative measures. If effectively implemented, this will make it possible to assess the impact of the rebranded policy, determine whether the new framework facilitates the use of alternative measures and evaluate their impact on the right to liberty.

FROM CONTROL TO AN EFFICIENT USE OF ALTERNATIVES

The proposal should be amended to realign with the genuine purpose of alternative measures, incorporating the following suggestions. Alternative measures must be firmly linked to the existence of detention grounds, coupled with clear time limits, to prevent arbitrary application. Priority should be given to human rights-respecting measures that minimise interference with the right to liberty, such as case management and community-based placement. Child-specific alternatives, such as forms of family-based placement, should also be included to ensure coherence with the best interest of the child principle. Including right-based alternatives directly into the Regulation will facilitate and ensure their use.

The ongoing negotiation presents a decisive moment to strengthen the legal framework governing alternative measures, ensuring that they function as a rights-based first-measure solution in the pre-removal phase. If their application increases, having a rights-based approach codified in the Regulation will help guarantee a consistent, proportionate, and human-rights-compliant policy.

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